

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Cytokinin depends on GA biosynthesis and signaling to regulate different aspects vegetative phase change in *Arabidopsis*

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Supplementary Figure 1. GA biosynthesis genes with unchanged expression in CK-deficient plants.

a-c Expression of GA biosynthesis genes in whole shoots of SD-grown Col-0, *ahk2,3* and CKX1ox plants. Numbers of biological replicates: Col-0 ($n_7 = 6$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 6$), CKX1ox ($n_7 = 6$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 4$), *ahk2 ahk3* ($n_7 = 5$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 5$). Transcript levels were determined by qRT-PCR. Data were normalized to *TAFIII5* and *PP2AA2*. Data displayed are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Dots indicate each single biological replicate. No statistically significant differences were observed compared to the wild type of the respective time point, as calculated by one-way ANOVA, post-hoc Dunnett's test.

Supplementary Figure 2. Expression of GA catabolism genes is altered by CK.

a-b Expression of GA catabolism genes in whole shoots of SD-grown Col-0, *ahk2,3* and CKX1ox plants. Numbers of biological replicates: Col-0 ($n_7 = 6$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 6$), CKX1ox ($n_7 = 6$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 4$), *ahk2 ahk3* ($n_7 = 5$; $n_{14} = 6$; $n_{21} = 5$). **c** Expression kinetics of GA catabolism genes in 10-day-old SD-grown wild-type seedlings after treatment with 1 μ M BA ($n = 6$ biological replicates). Transcript levels were determined by qRT-PCR. Data were normalized to *TAFIII5* and *PP2AA2*. Data displayed are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Dots indicate each single biological replicate. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences compared to the wild type of the respective time point (**a, b**), or compared to time point 0 (**c**), as calculated by one-way ANOVA, post-hoc Dunnett's test ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$; $***p < 0.001$).

Supplementary Figure 3. Concentration of GA metabolites in CK-deficient plants. Shown are concentrations of total GAs (**a**), bioactive forms of GA (**b**), 13-hydroxylated GAs (**c**) and non-13-hydroxylated GAs (**d**) in shoots of SD-grown plants ($n = 5$ biological replicates). Data displayed are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Dots indicate each single biological replicate. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences compared to the wild type of the respective time point, as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis test ($*q < 0.05$; $**q < 0.01$; $***q < 0.001$).

Supplementary Figure 4. Number of juvenile leaves in hybrid plants of *rock2* and the GA receptor mutant *gid1b gid1c*. Shown are the number of leaves without abaxial trichomes of SD-grown *rock2 gid1b,c* hybrid plants in comparison to their parents and wild type. In box plots, the center line represents the median value and the boundaries indicate the 25th percentile (upper) and the 75th percentile (lower). The X marks the mean value. Whiskers extend to the largest and smallest value, excluding outliers which are shown as dots. Letters indicate statistically significant differences between the genotypes, as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis test ($q < 0.05$).

Supplementary Figure 5. Genetic interactions between DELLA genes and CK receptor genes regarding vegetative phase change. Shown are the number of leaves without abaxial trichomes of SD-grown *ahk2,3 rga* (a), *ahk2,3 gai* (b) and *ahk2,3 rgl* (c) hybrid plants. In box plots, the center line represents the median value and the boundaries indicate the 25th percentile (upper) and the 75th percentile (lower). The X marks the mean value. Whiskers extend to the largest and smallest value, excluding outliers which are shown as dots. Letters indicate statistically significant differences between the genotypes, as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis test ($q < 0.05$).

Supplementary Figure 6. SPLs are required for CK to fully exert its influence on VPC. a, c Number of leaves without abaxial trichomes of SD-grown *rock2 spl2,10,11,13,15* (**a**) and *rock2 spl2,9,10,11,13,15* (**c**) hybrid plants in comparison to their respective parents and wild type. In box plots, the center line represents the median value and the boundaries indicate the 25th percentile (upper) and the 75th percentile (lower). The X marks the mean value. Whiskers extend to the largest and smallest value, excluding outliers which are shown as dots. **b, d** Length-to-width ratios of the blades of leaves 4 to 7. Data displayed are expressed as mean \pm SEM of SD-grown plants. Numbers of biological replicates: (**b**) Col-0 ($n_4 = 31$; $n_5 = 31$; $n_6 = 31$; $n_7 = 31$), *rock2* ($n_4 = 34$; $n_5 = 34$; $n_6 = 33$; $n_7 = 34$), *spl2,10,11,13,15* ($n_4 = 37$; $n_5 = 36$; $n_6 = 37$; $n_7 = 37$), *rock2 spl2,10,11,13,15* ($n_4 = 36$; $n_5 = 35$; $n_6 = 36$; $n_7 = 36$); (**d**) Col-0 ($n_4 = 36$; $n_5 = 35$; $n_6 = 37$; $n_7 = 38$), *rock2* ($n_4 = 36$; $n_5 = 36$; $n_6 = 35$; $n_7 = 36$), *spl2,9,10,11,13,15* ($n_4 = 38$; $n_5 = 37$; $n_6 = 38$; $n_7 = 38$), *rock2 spl2,9,10,11,13,15* ($n_4 = 35$; $n_5 = 34$; $n_6 = 35$; $n_7 = 35$). Letters indicate statistically significant differences between the genotypes, as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis test ($q < 0.05$) (**a, c**) or one-way ANOVA, post-hoc Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$) (**b, d**). In case of **b** and **d**, every leaf was analyzed separately.

Supplementary Figure 7. Confirmation of *GAI* knockout mutation in the *gai* mutant. **a** *GAI* transcript levels in LD-grown Col-0 or *gai* seedlings using primer pairs downstream (3') or upstream (5') of the T-DNA insertion or spanning the insertion site. Primers used are listed in Supplementary Table 4. No *GAI* full-length transcript is detectable in the mutant. Transcript levels were determined by qRT-PCR. Data were normalized to *TAFIII5* and *PP2AA2*. Data displayed are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n = 4 biological replicates). Dots indicate each single biological replicate. **b** Schematic presentation of *GAI* gene structure. It consists of solely one exon (white box), no introns. The T-DNA insertion in the *GAI* gene located at bp 272 is indicated by a triangle.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Concentrations of GA metabolites in shoots of plants grown under short-day conditions.

	7 DAG, shoot			14 DAG, shoot			21 DAG, shoot		
	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3
	8.71	ND	19.74	ND	ND	11.71	ND	19.54	ND
	13.24	ND	10.68	11.48	5.52	45.84	ND	8.42	ND
	ND	ND	8.37	9.72	ND	16.39	ND	ND	ND
	5.16	ND	ND	14.75	ND	8.91	13.64	19.80	ND
	ND	11.85	ND	9.83	ND	10.15	ND	ND	ND
GA1	9.03	11.85	12.93	11.45	5.52	18.60	13.64	15.92	-
SEM	2.34	0.00	3.47	1.17	0.00	6.93	0.00	3.75	-
	14.66	34.11	16.91	22.41	20.54	21.53	22.11	18.53	28.51
	24.73	19.22	28.07	15.78	14.28	25.78	14.62	28.85	23.46
	24.12	10.42	29.86	17.77	11.03	11.27	24.71	27.50	16.69
	17.79	24.50	55.42	16.16	21.31	13.77	15.90	16.29	13.43
	5.61	46.19	27.37	17.26	33.90	22.84	32.72	14.42	24.93
GA3	17.38	26.89	31.52	17.87	20.21	19.04	22.01	21.12	21.40
SEM	3.50	6.17	6.39	1.19	3.93	2.78	3.27	2.96	2.77
	167.28	53.98	102.81	130.04	35.50	197.04	76.68	43.38	40.17
	107.03	41.05	141.15	91.11	52.42	211.29	45.40	107.85	28.81
	119.90	60.54	133.04	189.95	42.20	103.77	72.50	50.34	30.74
	149.24	113.95	211.22	177.50	32.53	123.99	49.66	68.44	21.62
	233.89	245.51	81.18	195.15	47.47	107.72	113.01	18.03	18.91
GA4	155.47	103.01	133.88	156.75	42.02 **	148.76	71.45	57.61	28.05 **
SEM	22.29	37.73	22.11	20.04	3.68	22.98	12.06	14.94	3.74
	ND	6.33	5.03	2.92	10.76	ND	6.00	ND	7.40
	15.92	6.14	14.45	ND	ND	ND	ND	18.21	11.10
	12.84	14.00	6.14	5.31	ND	ND	5.73	12.80	7.90
	14.30	6.66	10.72	ND	5.53	ND	8.59	14.23	8.15
	13.98	17.56	6.80	10.14	6.44	ND	7.98	7.57	9.31
GA5	14.26	10.14	8.63	6.12	7.58	-	7.08	13.20	8.77
SEM	0.64	2.37	1.74	2.12	1.61	-	0.71	2.20	0.66
	355.70	365.26	357.58	197.14	270.37	207.66	198.94	247.18	193.68
	296.02	243.62	329.29	198.91	188.39	253.42	212.36	248.87	175.10
	241.33	338.61	345.31	277.26	174.14	185.98	262.26	168.98	264.06
	281.42	218.77	308.54	211.75	178.45	223.84	176.96	210.04	156.89
	329.80	385.36	256.81	223.43	226.54	301.75	229.11	176.66	181.01
GA6	300.85	310.32	319.51	221.70	207.58	234.53	215.93	210.35	194.15
SEM	19.74	33.38	17.69	14.68	18.22	20.09	14.39	16.86	18.46
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
GA7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SEM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	36.39	37.01	72.55	44.82	42.48	36.09	27.23	6.84	17.26
	33.03	39.14	72.75	53.11	30.68	47.55	31.29	22.46	37.45
	39.33	34.45	58.73	75.98	23.81	29.84	29.51	8.43	26.96
	22.00	47.87	82.71	49.14	34.87	30.97	19.54	7.93	15.97
	32.75	59.73	49.72	39.50	27.92	41.10	18.39	10.20	18.49
GA8	32.70	43.64	67.29 **	52.51	31.95 **	37.11 *	25.19	11.17 *	23.23
SEM	2.93	4.61	5.82	6.29	3.19	3.29	2.63	2.87	4.04
	18.11	9.83	ND	5.34	29.23	ND	ND	6.02	5.92
	9.87	10.86	12.58	ND	ND	ND	ND	22.38	ND
	5.57	15.71	5.98	5.13	ND	6.94	ND	ND	ND
	7.74	ND	83.25	9.97	ND	7.35	13.50	15.35	ND
	18.39	6.60	24.58	17.41	ND	17.20	17.63	5.45	ND
GA9	11.94	10.75	31.60	9.46	29.23	10.50	15.57	12.30	5.92
SEM	2.67	1.89	17.64	2.88	0.00	3.35	2.06	4.05	0.00

Supplementary Table 1. Continuation.

	7 DAG, shoot			14 DAG, shoot			21 DAG, shoot		
	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
GA12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SEM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	88.03	35.73	46.73	30.37	386.95	156.07	229.22	186.04	181.85
	49.68	30.67	31.96	28.02	299.70	204.80	202.99	175.12	100.74
	34.00	28.32	66.47	42.18	235.79	162.37	254.58	137.49	208.06
	45.34	17.15	47.03	18.37	155.44	133.66	146.33	152.28	72.31
	76.41	57.84	26.15	27.08	188.42	195.78	165.44	159.42	146.81
GA13	58.69	33.94	43.67	29.21	253.26 **	170.54 *	199.71	162.07	141.96
SEM	10.11	6.70	7.02	3.83	41.30	13.13	19.90	8.52	25.03
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
GA15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SEM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	47.83	35.22	37.29	108.20	73.28	142.56	70.11	38.58	91.60
	55.99	25.48	57.11	125.04	56.05	141.48	76.72	76.68	107.08
	56.02	24.77	41.93	123.72	81.90	116.20	122.44	30.88	100.45
	29.01	45.94	53.04	119.79	59.79	108.06	100.42	52.33	89.31
	30.27	54.58	55.81	97.82	68.57	176.91	64.91	55.35	70.04
GA19	43.82	37.20	49.04	114.91	67.92 *	137.04	86.92	50.77	91.70
SEM	5.98	5.81	3.97	5.20	4.65	12.07	10.76	7.87	6.28
	334.44	590.55	599.43	111.38	225.24	126.75	207.47	140.69	127.68
	190.22	328.65	488.05	161.04	139.13	111.83	60.45	115.17	119.80
	239.54	300.13	392.64	137.73	135.24	293.79	149.04	78.15	97.25
	297.50	239.84	492.23	95.02	100.56	272.38	78.14	109.33	140.05
	188.30	546.33	328.25	87.64	242.59	299.10	63.28	131.48	133.97
GA20	250.00	401.10 *	460.12 *	118.56	168.55	220.77	111.68	114.96	123.75
SEM	29.05	70.15	46.46	13.66	27.65	41.74	28.86	10.77	7.43
	5.22	11.29	ND	6.05	ND	ND	ND	ND	30.33
	5.58	ND	ND	15.11	8.08	6.68	8.38	18.23	11.55
	ND	ND	ND	6.01	7.87	5.20	16.24	ND	254.58
	8.11	ND	14.67	10.81	ND	9.22	-	ND	146.33
	ND	7.18	29.75	ND	ND	ND	39.11	9.11	165.44
GA24	6.31	9.24	22.21	9.49	7.98	7.03	21.24	13.67	121.64
SEM	0.91	2.06	7.54	2.18	0.10	1.17	9.22	4.56	45.09
	3.90	100.91	46.04	5.76	48.24	19.35	ND	11.68	28.43
	16.07	31.15	51.41	ND	25.94	19.09	9.01	13.71	14.11
	15.86	44.10	42.99	20.00	25.30	5.80	ND	14.30	ND
	21.32	28.79	54.26	17.48	6.20	5.55	18.93	11.46	8.20
	53.76	48.50	50.70	14.84	9.35	20.79	7.31	15.32	10.31
GA29	22.18	50.69	49.08	14.52	23.01	14.12	11.75	13.29	15.26
SEM	8.39	13.10	2.01	3.10	7.48	3.46	3.62	0.75	4.56
	278.49	18.51	160.29	222.39	38.77	97.40	39.49	10.98	18.45
	238.00	43.22	168.53	279.66	30.79	96.29	41.24	8.20	17.51
	262.72	47.58	160.20	316.46	33.40	96.62	51.11	9.61	17.17
	238.55	57.07	94.14	187.61	34.45	116.40	51.69	11.80	14.71
	169.74	58.14	117.86	297.91	32.82	127.78	39.76	7.46	19.99
GA34	237.50	44.90 ***	140.20 *	260.81	34.05 ***	106.90 *	44.66	9.61 ***	17.56 *
SEM	18.59	7.18	14.54	24.15	1.32	6.46	2.77	0.81	0.87

Supplementary Table 1. Continuation.

	7 DAG, shoot			14 DAG, shoot			21 DAG, shoot		
	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3	Col-0	CKX1ox	ahk2 ahk3
	17.16	74.85	38.66	38.56	34.44	21.97	20.33	19.28	48.14
	12.33	23.83	48.96	43.06	15.47	57.28	26.70	98.36	31.03
	7.59	48.93	48.86	83.06	10.88	52.81	33.81	30.89	56.07
	14.27	19.72	28.82	39.19	25.67	82.50	50.97	43.04	58.19
	26.87	38.62	101.47	56.71	41.94	119.26	24.31	66.76	43.46
GA44	15.64	41.19 *	53.35 **	52.12	25.68	66.76	31.22	51.67	47.38
SEM	3.21	9.90	12.59	8.40	5.76	16.27	5.40	14.08	4.88
	136.09	32.52	90.11	43.44	75.55	70.73	12.09	347.72	268.47
	200.78	50.75	46.06	38.84	81.07	59.76	20.08	322.57	335.08
	142.84	14.78	73.59	41.87	37.54	135.33	6.61	164.55	365.87
	59.94	92.59	28.17	225.89	75.90	119.82	16.91	118.58	316.36
	54.91	49.21	38.45	23.56	62.79	35.61	33.45	122.82	215.04
GA51	118.91	47.97	55.27	74.72	66.57	84.25	17.83	215.25 *	300.16 **
SEM	27.52	12.92	11.51	37.96	7.86	18.74	4.52	49.76	26.50
	12.31	14.51	10.60	21.27	7.38	13.95	10.51	3.82	33.91
	6.02	8.99	33.86	48.94	4.73	14.12	30.08	7.61	26.41
	2.67	8.78	5.12	30.19	11.48	45.20	28.74	4.96	20.37
	1.87	0.80	4.61	22.56	7.41	23.26	178.40	7.29	18.19
	7.29	9.63	7.44	29.77	4.77	23.40	52.68	4.88	11.85
GA53	6.03	8.54	12.32	30.55	7.16 **	23.98	60.08	5.71 **	22.15
SEM	1.87	2.20	5.49	4.94	1.23	5.70	30.33	0.74	3.75

Mean of 5 biological replicates is shown in bold type. Values are given as nmol x (g fresh weight)⁻¹. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences compared to the wild type of the respective time point, as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis test (* $q < 0.05$; ** $q < 0.01$; *** $q < 0.001$). ND = not detected.

Supplementary Table 2. Mutants and transgenic lines used in this study.

Genotype	Named in this study	Reference
<i>arr1-3 arr10-5 arr12-1</i>	<i>arr1,10,12</i>	Mason et al., 2005 ¹
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3</i>	<i>ahk2 ahk3</i>	Higuchi et al., 2004 ²
<i>rock2</i>	<i>rock2</i>	Bartrina et al., 2017 ³
<i>p35S:CKX1</i>	<i>CKX1ox</i>	Werner et al., 2003 ⁴
<i>ga1</i>	<i>ga1</i>	Willige et al., 2011 ⁵
<i>rock2 ga1</i>	<i>rock2 ga1</i>	this study
<i>ga3ox1-3 ga3ox2-1</i>	<i>ga3ox1,2</i>	Mitchum et al., 2006 ⁶
<i>rock2 ga3ox1-3 ga3ox2-1</i>	<i>rock2 ga3ox1,2</i>	this study
<i>gid1b-1 gid1c-2</i>	<i>gid1b gid1c</i>	Griffiths et al., 2006 ⁷
<i>rock2 gid1b-1 gid1c-2</i>	<i>rock2 gid1b,c</i>	this study
<i>gai</i>	<i>gai</i>	Matschi et al., 2015 ⁸
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 gai</i>	<i>ahk2,3 gai</i>	this study
<i>rga-28</i>	<i>rga</i>	Tyler et al., 2004 ⁹
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 rga-28</i>	<i>ahk2,3 rga</i>	this study
<i>gai rga-28</i>	<i>gai rga</i>	this study
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 gai rga-28</i>	<i>ahk2,3 gai rga</i>	this study
<i>spl2-1 spl10-2 spl11-1 spl13-1 spl15-1</i>	<i>spl2,10,11,13,15</i>	this study
<i>rock2 spl2-1 spl10-2 spl11-1 spl13-1 spl15-1</i>	<i>rock2 spl2,10,11,13,15</i>	this study
<i>spl2-1 spl9-4 spl10-2 spl11-1 spl13-1 spl15-1</i>	<i>spl2,9,10,11,13,15</i>	this study
<i>rock2 spl2-1 spl9-4 spl10-2 spl11-1 spl13-1 spl15-1</i>	<i>rock2 spl2,9,10,11,13,15</i>	this study
<i>toe1-2 toe2-1</i>	<i>toe1 toe2</i>	Aukerman & Sakai, 2003 ¹⁰
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 toe1-2 toe2-1</i>	<i>ahk2,3 toe1,2</i>	Werner et al., 2021 ¹¹
<i>gai rga-28 toe1-2 toe2-1</i>	<i>gai rga toe1,2</i>	this study
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 gai rga-28 toe1-2 toe2-1</i>	<i>ahk2,3 gai rga toe1,2</i>	this study
<i>rgl1-2</i>	<i>rgl1</i>	Tyler et al., 2004 ⁹
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 rgl1-2</i>	<i>ahk2,3 rgl1</i>	this study
<i>rgl2-13</i>	<i>rgl2</i>	Tyler et al., 2004 ⁹
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 rgl2-13</i>	<i>ahk2,3 rgl2</i>	this study
<i>rgl3-3</i>	<i>rgl3</i>	Tyler et al., 2004 ⁹
<i>ahk2-2tk ahk3-3 rgl3-3</i>	<i>ahk2,3 rgl3</i>	this study

Supplementary Table 3. Gene-specific and T-DNA primers used for genotyping in this study.

Locus	Allele	Primer pair	Sequences (5' → 3')	Fragment size
<i>AHK2</i> (AT5G35750)	WT (<i>ahk2-2tk</i>)	446_AHK2-ahk2-2tk-2_fw 447_AHK2-ahk2-2tk-2_rv	TGCCTTGTCTATTCTTGTATCT TAGGTTCAATTTCTTCAGTCC	719 bp
	<i>ahk2-2tk</i>	446_AHK2-ahk2-2tk-2_fw 230_T-DNA-ahk2-2tk_rv	TGCCTTGTCTATTCTTGTATCT ATAACGCTGCGGACATCTAC	~ 700 bp
<i>AHK3</i> (AT1G27320)	WT (<i>ahk3-3</i>)	397_AHK3-ahk3-3_fw 449_AHK3-ahk3-3_rv	GCAAGAATCCAGGTGCTAAC GCTATCAGTTACAACCCTTGC	771 bp
	<i>ahk3-3</i>	315_LBa1 449_AHK3-ahk3-3_rv	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG GCTATCAGTTACAACCCTTGC	~ 850 bp
<i>ARR1</i> (AT3G16857)	WT	309_ARR1-arr1-3_fw 310_ARR1-arr1-3_rv	CTTCAAGCACTAGCCGTCACAGGTCAGTT AATGTTATCGATGGAGTATGCGTCAAAGT	1306 bp
	<i>arr1-3</i>	309_ARR1-arr1-3_fw 315_LBa1	CTTCAAGCACTAGCCGTCACAGGTCAGTT TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	953 bp
<i>ARR10</i> (AT4G31920)	WT	311_ARR10-arr10-5_fw 312_ARR10-arr10-5_rv	CATTGGAGTTGTTGAGGGAGA CGATGATGAGACTGGTTGGA	1075 bp
	<i>arr10-5</i>	311_ARR10-arr10-5_fw 315_LBa1	CATTGGAGTTGTTGAGGGAGA TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	1230 bp
<i>ARR12</i> (AT2G25180)	WT	313_ARR12-arr12-1_fw 314_ARR12-arr12-1_rv	TAACAACGACGAACCAAGCA TTGGCAGAGTCACAGAATGG	1654 bp
	<i>arr12-1</i>	313_ARR12-arr12-1_fw 315_LBa1	TAACAACGACGAACCAAGCA TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	962 bp
<i>GA1</i> (AT4G02780)	WT	689_GA1-ga1_fw 691_GA1-ga1_rv	CGAGTAACCACTTCTCCTGT CTAACGCAAACCAATCTATC	962 bp
	<i>ga1-3</i>	689_GA1-ga1_fw 690_T-DNA-ga1_rv	CGAGTAACCACTTCTCCTGT GCTGTTGCCCGTCTCAC	704 bp
<i>GA3OX1</i> (AT1G15550)	WT	696_GA3OX1-ga3ox1-3_fw 697_GA3OX1-ga3ox1-3_rv	GTGTTTAGAGGCCATCCCATTAC CAAACAAATCATATTGCTGAAATC	1569 bp
	<i>ga3ox1-3</i>	696_GA3OX1-ga3ox1-3_fw 676_JMLB1	GTGTTTAGAGGCCATCCCATTAC GGCAATCAGCTGTTGCCCGTCTCACTGGTG	~ 1500 bp
<i>GA3OX2</i> (AT1G80340)	WT	698_GA3OX2-ga3ox2-1_fw 699_GA3OX2-ga3ox2-1_rv	GCCTTTTAGCATGAGTTCAAC AGATCATTATATCGGATGGTG	1357 bp
	<i>ga3ox2-1</i>	698_GA3OX2-ga3ox2-1_fw 315_LBa1	GCCTTTTAGCATGAGTTCAAC TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	~ 1800 bp
<i>GID1B</i> (AT3G63010)	WT	653_GID1B-gid1b-1_fw 654_GID1B-gid1b-1_rv	TCTCCTGTCCACCAAACATTG CTGGGTTTTGGAGACTATGGC	897 bp
	<i>gid1b-1</i>	655_SLAT-3' 654_GID1B-gid1b-1_rv	CTTATTTAGTAAGAGTGTGGGGTTTTGG CTGGGTTTTGGAGACTATGGC	354 bp

Supplementary Table 3. Continuation.

Locus	Allele	Primer pair	Sequences (5' → 3')	Fragment size
<i>GID1C</i> (AT5G27320)	WT	656_GID1C-gid1c-2_fw 657_GID1C-gid1c-2_rv	TCACCTTCCATGGTGGATATC CTTTTAACCGTCATCTCGCAG	983 bp
	<i>gid1c-2</i>	658_GABIKatLB1 657_GID1C-gid1c-2_rv	CCCATTTGGACGTCAATGTAGACAC CTTTTAACCGTCATCTCGCAG	671 bp
<i>GAI</i> (AT1G14920)	WT	661_GAI-gai_fw 663_GAI-gai_2_rv	ATGAAGAGAGATCATCATCAT AGCTTCGGCGAAGTAAGTAGC	648 bp
	<i>gai</i>	401_LB1-SAIL 662_GAI-gai_rv	GCCTTTTCAGAAATGGATAAAATAGCCTTGCTTCC ACCTTATCGATCGCACCAGGT	1064 bp
<i>RGA</i> (AT2G01570)	WT	664_RGA-rga-28_2_fw 665_RGA-rga-28_2_rv	TCACATAGAGAAGTCACATG CAGCTAAGCATCCGATTTGC	882 bp
	<i>rga-28</i>	660_RGA-rga-28_rv 400_LBb1.3-SALK	TGGTTCGCCGTGAAGTG ATTTTGCCGATTTCCGGAAC	~ 900 bp
<i>RGL1</i> (AT1G66350)	WT	667_RGL1-rgl1-2_fw 668_RGL1-rgl1-2_rv	GATATTC AAGAAGTTGGTTGG ACATTATACCCATCAGCCC	566 bp
	<i>rgl1-2</i>	667_RGL1-rgl1-2_fw 675_JMRB2	GATATTC AAGAAGTTGGTTGG TGATAGTGACCTTAGGCGACTTTTGAACGC	~ 700 bp
<i>RGL2</i> (AT3G03450)	WT	669_RGL2-rgl2-13_fw 670_RGL2-rgl2-13_rv	GTGGTGCTCGTTGACTCTC AACTCGGTCTTGACTCGG	861 bp
	<i>rgl2-13</i>	669_RGL2-rgl2-13_fw 315_LBa1	GTGGTGCTCGTTGACTCTC TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	~ 900 bp
<i>RGL3</i> (AT5G17490)	WT	671_RGL3-rgl3-3_fw 672_RGL3-rgl3-3_rv	CGAAGCCATCAAGAAAACG GTGAGACGAAACGACGGT	869 bp
	<i>rgl3-3</i>	671_RGL3-rgl3-3_fw 676_JMLB1	CGAAGCCATCAAGAAAACG GGCAATCAGCTGTTGCCCGTCTCACTGGTG	~ 500 bp
<i>SPL2</i> (AT5G43270)	WT	735_SPL2-spl2-1_fw 736_SPL2-spl2-1_rv	TGAATAGTGG AAGAGAGAAAAGCTTC CTTTAAACCGAGAACCGGATC	983 bp
	<i>spl2-1</i>	735_SPL2-spl2-1_fw 315_LBa1	TGAATAGTGG AAGAGAGAAAAGCTTC TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	~ 700 bp
<i>SPL9</i> (AT2G42200)	WT	420_SPL9-spl9-4_fw 421_SPL9-spl9-4_rv	TGGTTCCTCCACTGAGTCATC GCTCATTATGACCAGCGAGTC	1021 bp
	<i>spl9-4</i>	401_LB1-SAIL 421_SPL9-spl9-4_rv	GCCTTTTCAGAAATGGATAAAATAGCCTTGCTTCC GCTCATTATGACCAGCGAGTC	~ 650 bp
<i>SPL10</i> (AT1G27370)	WT	746_SPL10-spl10-2_fw 747_SPL10-spl10-2_rv	AGGACAAAACGATGCAATCTTG TTTTCTTCCGAGCAACAACAG	240 bp
	<i>spl10-2</i>	746_SPL10-spl10-2_fw 747_SPL10-spl10-2_rv	AGGACAAAACGATGCAATCTTG TTTTCTTCCGAGCAACAACAG	205 bp

Supplementary Table 3. Continuation.

Locus	Allele	Primer pair	Sequences (5' → 3')	Fragment size
<i>SPL11</i> (AT1G27360)	WT	741_SPL11-spl11-1_fw 742_SPL11-spl11-1_rv	GTTGCATTCTCTTTAGATTTTACTGTA GGACGAGGTTTTTATCATAGGTTTGG	955 bp
	<i>spl11-1</i>	741_SPL11-spl11-1_fw 743_T-DNA-spl11-1	GTTGCATTCTCTTTAGATTTTACTGTA TGTGCCAGGTGCCCCACGGAAATAGT	~ 200 bp
<i>SPL13A/B</i> (AT5G50570/ AT5G50670)	WT	748_SPL13-spl13-1_fw 749_SPL13-spl13-1_rv	TTCAAAGAGAACAAGAGGGA CTTAAACCATTAACACACAATCT	215 bp not cleaved by HpaI
	<i>spl13-1</i>	748_SPL13-spl13-1_fw 749_SPL13-spl13-1_rv	TTCAAAGAGAACAAGAGGGA CTTAAACCATTAACACACAATCT	176 + 39 bp cleaved by HpaI
<i>SPL15</i> (AT3G57920)	WT	422_SPL15-spl15-1_fw 423_SPL15-spl15-1_rv	TCCACCGAGTCTTCTTCACTC TGTTGGTGCTGAAGTTGCTG	1013 bp
	<i>spl15-1</i>	400_LBb1.3-SALK 423_SPL15-spl15-1_rv	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC TGTTGGTGCTGAAGTTGCTG	~ 800 bp
<i>TOE1</i> (AT2G28550)	WT	404_TOE1-toe1-2_fw 405_TOE1-toe1-2_rv	GAAGAGTTTGTGCATATACTGCG GAAGGGAAGTGAAAAGAGCCTC	569 bp
	<i>toe1-2</i>	400_LBb1.3-SALK 405_TOE1-toe1-2_rv	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC GAAGGGAAGTGAAAAGAGCCTC	~ 400 bp
<i>TOE2</i> (AT5G60120)	WT	406_TOE2-toe2-1_fw 407_TOE2-toe2-1_rv	AGTTGTGCTCTACACGAACGG TCCCAGCAGAAATCAGTTCAC	580 bp
	<i>toe2-1</i>	406_TOE2-toe2-1_fw 400_LBb1.3-SALK	AGTTGTGCTCTACACGAACGG ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	~ 350 bp
<i>ROCK2</i>	WT	263_rock2_fw 264_rock2_rv	TGGCTCAGAAATTGGGGATA TGATGGCTTCATATAAAAATATAACCATCTA	250 + 31 bp cleaved by XbaI
	<i>rock2</i>	263_rock2_fw 264_rock2_rv	TGGCTCAGAAATTGGGGATA TGATGGCTTCATATAAAAATATAACCATCTA	281 bp not cleaved by XbaI

Supplementary Table 4. qRT primers used for detection of gene transcripts in this study.

Gene	Primers	Sequences (5' → 3')
<i>PP2AA2</i> (AT3G25800)	478_PP2AA2-qRT_fw 479_PP2AA2-qRT_rv	CCATTAGATCTTGTCTCTCTGCT GACAAAACCCGTACCGAG
<i>TAFII15</i> (AT4G31720)	339_TAFII15-qRT_fw 340_TAFII15-qRT_rv	gaatcacggccaacaatc actcttagccaagtagtgctcc
<i>GA1</i> (AT4G02780)	842_GA1-qRT6_fw 843_GA1-qRT6_rv	CCTAACTAACTTCTTCACCCACAC AGGAAGACAGATTTCGATTGATG
<i>GA2</i> (AT1G79460)	785_GA2-qRT_fw 786_GA2-qRT_rv	TGAGCACTATGGGTCGTCTTC ACCACACTTCCTTTCTCCTCC
<i>GA3</i> (AT5G25900)	787_GA3-qRT_fw 788_GA3-qRT_rv	CCCATTCGCTACGCCCA TCTCCCAACGCTTCTTATCCA
<i>KAO1</i> (AT1G05160)	789_KAO1-qRT_fw 790_KAO1-qRT_rv	GTGCGTTCCTTCCTTTTGGT ATCACTGGACATTTCGGGGTT
<i>KAO2</i> (AT2G32440)	791_KAO2-qRT_fw 792_KAO2-qRT_rv	GAAATGGGTGCTGAAGAGAGTG GGTGATGTAGGATTGGATGAAGG
<i>GA2ox1</i> (AT4G25420)	812_GA2ox1-qRT_fw 813_GA2ox1-qRT_rv	GCTACGCAAGCAGTTTCACC ATGTCCCAACGCATCGCA
<i>GA2ox2</i> (AT5G51810)	814_GA2ox2-qRT_fw 815_GA2ox2-qRT_rv	AGAGCGGTTGTGAATAGAGAGAG TCAAGGAACATAGACCAAGTGAAG
<i>GA3ox1</i> (AT1G15550)	701_GA3ox1-qRT_fw 702_GA3ox1-qRT_rv	TTGGGGTCAGCGAAGAAGA ACAGAATGGTTAGGAGGGTGG
<i>GA3ox2</i> (AT1G80340)	893_GA3ox2-qRT5_6_fw 894_GA3ox2-qRT5_rv	GCCACCACCTCAAATACTGTG ATGAGGGTCGAGTCTGTATGG
<i>GA2ox1</i> (AT1G78440)	872_GA2ox1-qRT2_fw 873_GA2ox1-qRT2_rv	AACGTTGGTGACTCTCTCCAGGTG AACCCTATGCCTCACGCTCTTG
<i>GA2ox2</i> (AT1G30040)	874_GA2ox2-qRT2_fw 875_GA2ox2-qRT2_rv	AGATGGAAGTTGGGTCGCTGTC CCCGTTAGTCATAACCTGAAGAGC
<i>GAI 5' end</i> (AT1G14920)	683_GAI-5'-qRT_fw 684_GAI-5'-qRT_rv	TGAATGAAGAAGACGACGGTAA CGGTGAGCATAGAATCAAGCC
<i>GAI T-DNA spanning</i> (AT1G14920)	687_GAI-T-DNA-qRT_fw 688_GAI-T-DNA-qRT_rv	CTTGATTCTATGCTCACCGACC CACCGTTCTCCTGCGAGT
<i>GAI 3' end</i> (AT1G14920)	685_GAI-3'-qRT_fw 686_GAI-3'-qRT_rv	TTCGGCTTCTTCGTCTAACC TGCGAGTCAACCAGGACAA

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